

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF ACID-BASE BALANCE

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Annotation. Metabolic processes in the human body continuously lead to the formation of acids and, to a lesser extent, to the formation of bases. The hydrogen ion (H^+) is particularly reactive; it binds to negatively charged proteins and, if present in high concentration, changes their overall charge, configuration and function.

Keywords. Carbohydrates, Fats, buffer systems

Relevance. Most acids are synthesized due to metabolism: Carbohydrates and Fats. Every day, carbohydrate-fat metabolism generates from 15,000 to 20,000 mmol of carbon dioxide (CO_2). CO_2 itself is not an acid, but in the presence of a member of the carbonic anhydrase family of enzymes, CO_2 combines with water (H_2O) in the blood to form carbonic acid (H_2CO_3), which breaks down into hydrogen ion (H^+) and bicarbonate (HCO_3^-). H^+ binds to hemoglobin in red blood cells and is released by oxygenation in the alveoli, at the same time this reaction is inverted by another carbonic anhydrase reaction, creating water (H_2O), excreted from the body through the kidneys, and CO_2 , which is eliminated with each exhalation of air. Chemical buffer systems are solutions that dampen pH changes. Intra- and extracellular buffer systems immediately respond to disturbances in acid-base balance. Bones also perform an important buffering function, especially when overloaded with acids. The buffer system consists of a weak acid and an associated base. The base adds H^+ , and the weak acid removes it, thereby minimizing changes in the concentration of free H^+ . The buffer system allows minimizing changes in pH near the equilibrium constant (pK_a); thus, although many buffer pairs potentially exist in the body, only a few are physiologically significant.

The purpose of this study. Acid-base balance is an important parameter that is maintained in human blood within certain limits. This is necessary for the normal functioning of various body systems, the occurrence of biochemical reactions, and the optimal functioning of enzymes.

Materials and methods of research. It is ensured by a certain ratio of acids and bases in biological media, if it is violated (pH goes beyond 6.8 - 7.8) the organism dies. Violations of the CBS are observed in many diseases, aggravate their course and are subject to correction. Depending on the direction of the shift in pH (hydrogen index) of the blood, disorders of the acid-base state are divided into acidosis and alkalosis. If the blood pH does not fall outside the normal range (7.35 - 7.45), acidosis or alkalosis is called compensated. If the regulatory mechanisms are insufficient and pH deviations become pronounced, then such conditions are called decompensated. According to the mechanism of development, acidosis or alkalosis can be gas (respiratory), which develops when the metabolism and transport of CO_2 is impaired, and non-gas (metabolic), which occurs when non-volatile products of an acidic and basic nature accumulate in the body.

Conclusion. Along with powerful and fast-acting chemical systems, organ mechanisms function in the body to compensate and eliminate shifts in the acid-rich hormone system. To implement them and achieve the desired effect, more time is required - from several minutes

to several hours. The most effective physiological mechanisms for regulating acid-rich hormones include processes occurring in the lungs, kidneys, liver and gastrointestinal tract.

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